

**THE UTILIZATION OF SOME ALIEN INVASIVE PLANTS SPECIES AROUND
THULAMELA LOCAL MUNICIPALITY OF LIMPOPO PROVINCE, SOUTH
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BY

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1 INTRODUCTION

Alien plant is a collective term used to describe plants that are not indigenous to the country. Some of this plants arrived by accidents in South Africa but the majority of introductions were deliberate, for reasons which appeared good at that time or to serve human needs (Ewel 1999).

According to Richartson *et al.* (2000) and Rejmanek *et al.* (2004) there are various terminologies associated with alien plants invasion:

- Alien plants: these are plant taxa whose occurrence in a given area results from their introduction (intentionally or accidentally) by human activity (synonyms: exotic plants, nonnative plants, non indigenous plants).
- Casual plants: these are alien plants that may flourish in an area but do not persists for more than one life cycle without further introduction (includes taxa labeled in the literature as waifs, occasional escapes, and persisting after cultivation)
- Naturalized plants: alien plants that reproduce and sustain populations over more than one life cycle without intervention by humans or despite human intervention: they often recruit offspring freely, but often just near adult plants, and do not necessarily invade natural, semi natural, or human made ecosystem.
- Weeds: these are plants that are undesirable from a human point of view. They are usually taxa with detectable economic or environmental effects

(synonyms: pest, harmful species, or problem plants). Environmental weeds are alien plants taxa that invade natural vegetation, usually adversely affecting native biodiversity or ecosystem functioning.

- Invasive plants: alien plants that recruit reproductive offspring, often in very large numbers, at considerable distances from parent plants and thus have the potential to spread rapidly.
- Transformer species: a subset of invasive plants that change the character, condition, form, or natural ecosystems over a substantial area relative to the extent of ecosystem.

These plants have been referred by Westbrooks (1991) as biological pollutants. In some cases, exotic plant invaders are driving our rarest species closer to extinction. Biological invasions are also widely recognized as the second largest global threat to biodiversity. In many parts of the world, the most challenging and time-consuming tasks of conservation biologists and managers are those relating to controlling alien species, preventing impacts and, increasing, repairing systems damaged by aliens. South Africa has a long history of problems with invasive alien species, and of research and management of biological invasion (Van Wilgen and Richardson 1985).

Invasive alien plants are a problem of global significance. In South Africa, at least 161 species cause serious problems in natural and semi-natural systems (Henderson 1995),

impacting on million hectares (80%) of the country (Le maitre *et al.* 2000). The cost to clear these invaders in South Africa is estimated to be around US\$ 1.2 billion, or roughly US\$ 60 million per year for the estimated 20 years of dealing with the problem (Versfeld *et al.* 1998). Impact associated with invasive alien plants include reduced surface water runoff and groundwater reserves, increased biomass and fire intensity, markedly reduced biodiversity and many economic consequences. The provision of recreational opportunities is another important ecosystem service that is often adversely affected by invasion. For example, recreational fishing is a pastime of large numbers of people, and supports of a significant economic sector. Opportunities for fishing are affected by invasion of water bodies by floating aquatic species, and of river banks by alien plants tree. Such impacts have potentially significant economic knock-on effects for the creations of ecotourism opportunities, which can be significant. South Africa has unusually high level of biodiversity, and alien plants could eliminate several thousand species of plants if spread is not controlled, seriously affecting the delivery of ecosystem services (Henderson 1995).

The success of some alien plants as invaders is least partly, attributable to their life history traits that allow them to establish, grow, reproduce, spread and eventually dominate in new environment. For example, many widespread and damaging invaders produce large numbers of highly dispersible seeds and can capitalize on disturbance events such as fire or floods to enhance reproduction and spread. Alien plants are often presents in a new environment for some time before they start spreading. During this lag

phase, there may be selection for certain attributes that enhanced invasive potential, or it may take some time to develop the necessary interaction with local biota (such as pollinators or seed dispersal agents) that facilitates invasion (Gordon 1999).

Invasion by alien plants in South Africa, as elsewhere in the whole world, results in many negative impacts and they also increases the negative impacts of fires, by increasing fuel loads that lead to high fire intensities, making the fires more difficult to control and increasing the risk of damage (Van Wilgen and Richardson 1985). The more intense fires also cause severe damage to soils (Scott *et al.* 2000), leading to soil loss (Euston-brown 2000), and severe soils erosion during rainstorms and damage to infrastructure due to flooding.

There are more than 117 invasive alien plants identified as major invaders (i.e. those that are well established and already have substantial impact) and approximately 84 species as emerging (i.e. those that currently have less impact but have attributes and a potentially suitable habitat that could increase their future impact). Of these major invasive alien plants identified, 29 species are considered to be aggressive transformers i.e. those that change the characters, conditions, form or nature of ecosystems over a substantial area relative to extent of those ecosystems. These invaders have claimed about 8% or 10 million hectares of land suitable for agricultural use in South Africa. This is an equivalent of every square inch of available land in our province. If they are not eradicated or

managed, in fifteen years they would have doubled. Together these invasive alien plants steal about seven percent of our water bulk every year. However ISAP (Invasive Alien Species Programme) has adopted a range of methods to control invasive alien plants.

These include:

- Mechanical methods-felling, removing (for example, cutting and slashing) or burning invading alien plants.
 - Chemical methods-using ecologically safe and registered herbicides.
 - Biological control-using host specific insects and pathogens from the alien country of origin. to date 76 bio-control agents have been released in south Africa
 - Integrated control-combinations of the above three approaches. Often an integrated approach is required in order to prevent enormous impacts.
- ([Www.agric.za/agisweb/wip](http://www.agric.za/agisweb/wip)).

Invasive alien plants are widespread in Limpopo, both in cultivation and the wild. According to the Department of Water and Forestry Working for Water annual report (2003/2004), alien plant cover in Thulamela Local Municipality (TLM) constitutes 1-5 percent plant cover ratio. However, the majority does not pose a threat but a few, by virtue of their aggressive qualities, have the capacity to invade natural habitats and overwhelm some, or even all of the indigenous vegetation. Invasive alien plants usually have much greater potential for invasion than indigenous plants because they have not had time to settle into equilibrium in their new community. These invaders come in many

shapes and sizes. They may be trees, shrubs, small herbaceous plants or waterweeds but they have in common the ability to spread and reproduce rapidly.

Although these plants are aliens or exotic, studies have shown that they may also have economical, social and ecological significance. The invasion by alien plants in Thulamela Local Municipality as elsewhere in South Africa, result in many negative impacts as shown above. In addition, some invasive plants also have major positive benefits, and these need to be taken in to account when assessing the costs resulting from invasions.

Alien plants around Thulamela local municipality, as it is the case with the whole of South Africa, has become a central issue in conservation of our indigenous plants or native plants. They cause major threat to our indigenous plants both in aquatic and terrestrial ecosystem and their management becomes costly and labour intensive. Local and national government are spending more money trying to eradicate them completely.

For this particular study, the following research questions were investigated:

- What are the various types of alien plants that are available?
- What are the utilization categories of alien plants growing around Thulamela local municipality if there is any?
- What are their market potential?

The aim of the project was to investigate the utilization of alien plants around Thulamela local municipality in Limpopo province, South Africa.

The following objectives were investigated in order to achieve the aim:

- Documentation of alien plants found around Thulamela local municipality.
- Identification of alien plants that are utilized around Thulamela local municipality.
- Classification of utilization options of such alien species.

The hypothesis is that some of the alien plants around Thulamela local municipality may be controlled by integrating their wise utilization as an option.

To justify the study it is therefore important to investigate how alien plants can be controlled by exploiting their utilization around Thulamela local municipality rather than completely eradicating them from the communities that have developed reliance upon them for various purposes. Exploiting their utilization may have a good effect to the socio-economic status of local people. It is a fact that plants can be ecologically, socially and economically significant, irrespective of whether they are native or not (Crooks 2002). It has also been recorded that alien plant species are used in agro forestry for functions and services that cannot be provided by native species. Therefore it is wise to utilize this unwanted plant rather than completely destroying them. In utilizing them we will be reducing the cost of buying the chemicals and expensive equipments for destroying them.

2 STUDY AREA

The study was conducted in villages which are located within the Thulamela Local Municipality (Figure 1). TLM is one of the four local municipalities which constitute the Vhembe District Municipality of [Limpopo](#) province of [South Africa](#). It is situated in the northeastern part of Limpopo province.

Figure 1: Villages within Thulamela local municipality

(http://thulamela.limpopo.gov.za/_images/tourism/places_of_interest/thulamela_municipality_places_of_interest.jpg).

Within the Vhembe district municipality, TLM carries the highest population ratio (Table 1) as per census 2001.

Table 1: Population distribution within the four local municipalities that constitute the Vhembe district municipality

(http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Vhembe_District_Municipality).

Local municipality	Population	Percentage (%)
Thulamela	584 568	48.72%
Makhado	497 093	41.43%
Mutale	78 917	6.58%
Musina	39 308	3.28%

3 MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1 Materials

The following materials and tools were developed and used in the collection of data on alien species around Thulamela Local Municipalities:

1. Questionnaires were used in collection of data used in the compilation of the database.
2. Digital camera was used in taking pictures.
3. Plant press was used in preparing voucher specimens that were deposited in the university of Venda herbarium.
4. Plant identification books and keys were used in identifying specimens.

3.2 Methods

Open ended questionnaires were administered on members of the communities within Thulamela local municipality. Areas within Thulamela Local Municipality were identified for sample collection. People within TLM were interviewed. The interview took into consideration knowledge holders on utilization of alien plants. A traditional healer was interviewed using an open ended approach. He was asked about the utilization of alien invasive plants that were sampled during the survey for voucher specimens. Voucher specimens were collected using procedures of collection, pressing and drying.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Data on utilization of alien invasive plants was collected through interviews from nineteen people and one traditional healer. From the interviews sixteen alien invasive species were recorded. Voucher specimens of alien plants were deposited in the University of Venda Herbarium in the department of Botany. The alien invasive plant species recorded were used in the creation of database which looked into their common names, family, scientific names, their utilization and parts used.

1. Scientific name: *Pinus sylvaticus*.

Common name: Pine (E), Mupaini (V), Mopine (NS).

Family: Pinaceae.

Utilization: Pine wood is used in high-value carpentry items such as furniture and window frames. Small pine trees are harvested during and used in decoration. A tea is made by steeping, green pine needle in boiling water. The resins are collected and used medicinally by traditional healers

Part/s utilized: Wood, leaves and resins.

2. Scientific name: *Jacaranda mimosifolia*.

Common name: Jacaranda (E), Jakaranda (A), Mudzhakaranda (V), Mojakaranta (NS).

Family: Bignoniaceae.

Utilization: The plant is utilized for ornamental purposes because of its beautiful blue flowers. They are usually grown in the parks and also in homes for provision of shade. Majority of people also dry these plants for the use as firewood.

Part/s utilized: The entire plant.

3. Scientific name: *Araujia sp.*

Common name: Cruel plant (E).

Family: Apocynaceae.

Utilization: Ornamental.

Part/s utilized: Entire plant.

4. Scientific name: *Caesalpinia decapetala.*

Common name: Marititius thorn (E), Kraaldoring (A), luanakha (V).

Family: Fabaceae.

Utilization: The stem and roots are used for medicinal purposes. Cattle herders also use seeds as a source of lubricant and soap after swimming in natural rivers.

It is also used as security hedging around homes.

Part/s utilized: Seeds, roots and entire plant.

5. Scientific name: *Lantana camara.*

Common name: Lantanta (E), Cherry pie (E), Tshidzimbambule (V).

Family: Verbenaceae.

Utilization: It is used for ornamental in gardens and indoors. Small branches are bundled together to make brooms. The leaves are also used as a medicine in the treatment of flu and fevers. In some communities it used as firewood and hedging.

Part/s utilized: Flower, roots, leaves, branches and entire plant.

6. Scientific name: *Ricinus communis*.

Common name: Castor bean (E), Casterolieboom (A), Mupfure (V), Mo-oli (NS).

Family: Euphorbiaceae.

Utilization: The seeds are used as source of oil (Castor-oil). The fruit of this tree is used by children as slingshot balls. It is also used for medicinal purposes.

Leaves and stems are used as remedy against stings and bite of insects and animals.

Part/s utilized: Seeds, Fruits, stem and leaves.

7. Scientific name: *Sesbania punicea*.

Common name: Red sesbania (E), Rooisesbania (A).

Family: Fabaceae.

Utilization: For ornamental and shade purposes.

Part/s utilized: The entire plant.

8. Scientific name: *Solanum mauritianum*.

Common name: Bugweed (E), Luisboom (A), Mututulwa (V).

Family: Solanaceae.

Utilization: The fruits are used to feed domestic doves. And the tree is also planted for the use as ornamental. It is also used for medicinal purposes.

Part/s utilized: Seeds, flowers and leaves.

9. Scientific name: *Optunia ficus-indica*.

Common name: Optunia (E), Mudoro (V), Motloro (NS).

Family: Cactaceae.

Utilization: Sweet fruits of this plant are used as source of food.

Part/s utilized: Fruits.

10. Scientific name: *Xanthium strumarium*.

Common name: Kankerroos (A), Rough cocklebur (E).

Family: Asteraceae.

Utilization: It is used for medicinal purposes.

Part/s utilized: Leaves.

11. Scientific name: *Senna didymobotrya*.

Common name: Peanut butter cassia (E), Rondboontjieberkassia (A).

Family: Fabaceae.

Utilization: It is used for medicinal purposes.

Part/s utilized: Leaves.

12. Scientific name: *Melia azedarach*.

Common name: Sering (A), Seringa (E), Muserenga (V).

Family: Meliaceae

Utilization: This tree is used for medicinal purposes, ornamental and to provide shade.

Part/s utilized: Roots are used for medicines, and the entire plants is used for ornamental and shading.

13. Scientific name: *Psidium guajava*.

Common name: Guava (E), Koejawel (A), Mugwavha (V).

Family: Myrtaceae.

Utilization: Its edible fruit are used as source of food and the tree as a whole is planted to provide shade.

Part/s utilized: Fruits are eaten as food and the entire tree is preferred as a shade.

14. Scientific name: *Eucalyptus paniculata*.

Common name: Grey iron bark (E), grysterbasbloekom (A), Mubomo (V).

Family: Myrtaceae.

Utilization: Leaves and resins are used for medicinal purposes. In most communities this tree is used as firewood, for ornamental purposes as well as source of shade.

Part/s utilized: Leaves, resins, and twigs.

15. Scientific name: *Rubus cuneifolius*.

Common name: American bramble (E), Amerikaanse braam (A), Munambela (V).

Family: Rosaceae.

Utilization: The plant is used as source of fruits and it is also utilized for medicinal purposes.

Part/s utilized: Fruits and leaves.

16. Scientific name: *Nerium oleander*.

Common name: Oleander (E)

Family: Apocynaceae.

Utilization: This plant is used as ornamental in the gardens. The leaves are also used medicinally.

Part/s utilized: The entire plant.

Table 2: utilization category of invasive alien plants and their frequency around Thulamela local municipality.

Utilization category	Frequency (n)
Medicinal.	Eleven
Ornamental.	Eight
Lubricant.	Two
Furniture.	One
Firewood.	Three
Food.	Four
Shading.	Four
Recreational.	One

Table 2 reveal eight utilization categories expressed by members of the communities. Top on the list of utilization categories is the use of alien invasive species in traditional medicines (eleven species) followed by those that are used for ornamental purposes (eight species).

Figure 2: Percentage utilization of alien plants around Thulamela Local Municipality from data collected in 2008 study.

The graph in figure 2 reflects percentages of various utilization categories of alien invasive plants around Thulamela Local Municipality of which the highest utilization category is for medicinal purposes (31%). It therefore suggests that the majority of people in Thulamela Local Municipality utilize alien invasive plants to meet their medicinal needs and those of their livestock. The second high rank of utilization of alien invasive plants is for ornamental (23%). They are typically grown in flower gardens and as house plants to provide shade and most commonly they are grown for display of their colorful flowers. Some of them are planted as they remain evergreen throughout the year and due to their wide range of tolerance to many environmental trends or catastrophic.

Communities also plant alien invasive plants intentionally to provide shade and as wind breaks. They also exploit them as source of food due to their edibility. Most of alien invasive plants are collected for use as firewood. While the least utilization categories are for furniture and recreations.

Table 3: Plants parts utilization of alien invasive plants around Thulamela Local Municipality from data collected in 2008 study.

Plant parts	Frequency
Leaves	Eight
Fruits	Four
Roots	Three
Entire plants	Nine
Twigs or Branches	Two
Flowers	Two
Resins	Two
Stem	Two
Seeds	Three

As revealed in table 3 in most cases the entire plant (n = 9) is utilized for various purposes. These are cases where plants are used for ornamental and shades. Leaves (n = 8) are also utilized in a number of species since they follow closely on those species that are entirely utilized.

Figure 3: A pie-chart indicating plants parts utilization on alien invasive plants around Thulamela municipality from data collected in 2008 study.

The most plant parts utilized are leaves. The leaves are used for a wide range of purposes including feeding livestock's and also utilized for medicinal purposes. In some cases the plant is utilized entirely. The utilization of the whole plant is mainly for ornamental e.g. as house plants.

Fruits are used seasonally as a source of food. Similarly flowers, resins, branches and seeds are also used seasonally to meet the needs e.g. for medicine and food. The least part of alien invasive plants utilized is stem bark which is used only for furniture.

Figure 4: Alien invasive plants most frequently utilized as per data collected in 2008 study.

According to figure 4 *Lantana camara* is frequently utilized around Thulamela Local Municipality due to its diverse utilization categories as compared to other invaders. While *Solanum mauritanum*, *Pinus sylvaticus* and *Eucalyptus paniculata* are equally utilized, all invaders that are frequently utilized has a market potential to the local people during specific period. Four species fall in the third category of alien invasive plants most frequently utilized as indicated in figure 4.

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS.

Problems associated with alien invasive plants including increase in fuel load, result in natural fire, reduction of ground water table, extinctions and encroachment upon endangered and threatened species. Most of all it changes the natural ecological processes such as plants community succession. Therefore, it is vital that an effective integrated strategic approach is adopted when managing and controlling these plant invaders in order to minimize their impact on biodiversity and ecosystem as a whole.

Human activities such as plantation of alien invasive plants for ornamentals and for commercial purposes have played a significant role in determining the current invasion pattern around Thulamela Local Municipality and will continue to do so in future. Well indeed, effective actions need to be taken in order to control and reduce their spread, or else the situation will be worse.

The finding of this research provides a means of improving our effort to deal with alien invasive plants in an effective way, and the time and cost required to control them can be considerably reduced.

Investigations of the strategies on how to control and manage alien invasive plants is very crucial and more studies are needed in Thulamela Local Municipality to get a broader picture of alien invasive plants and their impact on the environment. People will therefore be able to recognize potential invaders early and take precautionary measures.

Communities must be encouraged to use alternative, non invasive species for ornamental and utilitarian purposes. Integrated control-combinations of four approaches (biological control, mechanical methods, chemical methods and utilization technique) are required in order to prevent enormous impacts of these invaders in Thulamela Local Municipality and South Africa as a whole.

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